

PHILOSOPHICAL ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE VICTIMOLOGICAL PREVENTION SYSTEM IN ENSURING THE STABILITY OF THE SOCIO-SPIRITUAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN

Toshpulatov Khusanboy Juraboyevich

Researcher at Fergana State University

Orcid ID: 0009-0002-6980-849X

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14667491>

Abstract: The article studies the theoretical and methodological foundations of ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in society, victimological prevention and its dialectical features in ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in society, and the prospects for improving the victimological prevention system in ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment. Modern conceptual approaches and views on ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in society are also analyzed.

Key words: society, socio-spiritual environment, social laws, victimological prevention, traditionalism and modernity, comparative analysis, analysis and synthesis, systemic and functional, dialectical nature, stability.

INTRODUCTION. Ensuring peace and tranquility in society, unconditional respect for human rights and freedoms, further socio-economic development of the country, improving the well-being of the population, increasing the legal awareness and legal culture of the population, serving the well-being of the people, and achieving the goals set by the comprehensive reforms being implemented to build the New State of Uzbekistan are among the most important requirements today.

In particular, the adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6196 dated March 26, 2021 "On measures to raise the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of ensuring public safety and combating crime to a qualitatively new level" in order to ensure public safety, prevent crimes and form an integrated system of combating crime, establish effective activities of internal affairs bodies from the lowest level to the Republican level, and introduce modern working methods in our country, ensuring peace and tranquility of the population, expanded the possibilities for a more effective organization of the system of ensuring public safety and preventing crimes and combating crime.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Theoretical and methodological foundations of ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in

society, victimological prevention and its dialectical features in ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in society, the origin of cases of violence against minors and child victimization, issues related to the importance of ensuring the rights of the child in international law T.V. Varchuk, E.N. Yershova, L.S. Alekseyeva, B. Neil, A.L. Genley, B. Fortson, J. Klevens, M. Merrick, L. Gilbert, S. Alexander, S. Graham, S. Limber, P. Olvis, L.V. Frank, D.V. Rivman, Y.M. Antonyan, V.S. Ustinov, I.A. Fargiyev, V.I. Polubinsky, Q.R. Abdurasulova, I.U. Ismailov, J.S. Mukhtorov, S.B. Khojakulov, It has been analyzed in the scientific works of scientists such as D.R. Turayeva and Sh.K. Giyasov.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. It is worth noting that currently one of the main tasks of the crime prevention system is to ensure security in society, in particular, to maintain peace and tranquility of the population, to ensure stability in each region, to protect the freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens, that is, their life, health, honor and dignity, and property from various forms of aggression. However, it is no secret that the rise of international crime, such as religious extremism, terrorism, human trafficking, drug trafficking, and arms trafficking, which have become a global problem today, poses a great threat to the security, stability, fundamental reforms being carried out, and the life, health, and other constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens. Currently, religious extremists are using terrorism, one of the most heinous forms of crime. As a result, international unrest has arisen and various disasters have befallen the biological entity called humanity. As a result, the number of victims of this type of international crime is increasing year by year. In addition, as a result of the commission of certain types of crimes, including intentional homicide, intentional bodily harm, defamation, assault, hooliganism, robbery, theft, fraud, extortion, vehicle theft, vehicle hijacking and other crimes, as well as persons who have committed offenses provided for in the Code of Administrative Responsibility, victims of these types of offenses are being subjected to physical, moral or property damage. In order to prevent such negative situations, in particular, to reduce and prevent the risk of individuals becoming victims of various types of offenses, victimological prevention of offenses is currently being carried out by the preventive services of the internal affairs bodies.

The legal basis for identifying the factors that lead to the emergence or occurrence of violence and related offenses in the field of ensuring the stability of the socio-spiritual environment in the new Uzbekistan and implementing the prevention of offenses is provided by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Laws “On Internal Affairs Bodies”, “On Prevention of Offenses”,

the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence” No. 561 dated September 2, 2019, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Measures to Improve the System of Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence” No. 3 dated January 4, 2020, the Laws “On Prevention of Neglect and Offenses among Minors”, “Combating Human Trafficking”, “Combating Terrorism and Extremism “On” and decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Criminal Procedure Code, the Criminal Code, the Code of Administrative Responsibility, the Family Code, as well as orders of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and other regulatory legal acts.

Also, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-27 dated March 29, 2021, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan and the tasks set forth therein, the decrees and resolutions adopted in order to further improve the system of internal affairs bodies and bring it to new levels, and to put modern experiences into practice in combating new aspects of crime, the concept and the tasks set forth therein are also considered a legal basis.

As our President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev noted, where there is no knowledge, there will be backwardness, ignorance, evil, and, of course, deviation from the right path. As we think about solving one of the most complex and important issues that our rapidly changing life poses to us today, we are once again convinced that their solution lies precisely in education, in shaping the worldview of young people on the basis of modern knowledge, high spirituality and enlightenment, and emphasize the great role of the family in this, and that crimes against family life and family separations have a great impact on future generations. Despite the important work being done in this regard, a number of systemic problems remain that hinder the effectiveness of spiritual and educational reforms in the process of renewal in the social, economic and political spheres. One of these, maintaining peace in the family is the highest blessing, and all employees of internal affairs bodies should serve the interests of the people, and this was also determined as a priority task in the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan.

As Eastern sages have noted, the greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, and the greatest inheritance is good upbringing. Therefore, in order not to make mistakes in life, every person should regularly work on himself and aim to achieve high heights, along with life lessons, to become truly enlightened and a possessor of high culture.

Guilty victimization consists of the negative, legally and morally inappropriate behavior of a potential victim, which is a factor that allows a crime to be committed. For example, most citizens suffer from traffic accidents as a result of their failure to comply with traffic rules.

Innocent victimization is generally associated with the nature of the labor or public activity of a particular person (for example, a collector, a neighborhood watchman) who has socially acceptable morality in life and in the situation before the crime, or with psychophysical aspects (for example, a child, an elderly person, a sick person, etc.).

CONCLUSION. In the national legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a victim of a crime is understood as a person who has suffered physical, moral or property damage as a result of a crime. It is worth noting that a number of criminological studies have paid special attention to persons who have suffered violence within the framework of domestic relations. Some criminologists include individuals who have suffered damage directly as a result of a crime as victims of crime, while others recognize that a victim is an individual who has been recognized as having suffered damage as a result of criminal aggression in a legally binding indictment.

From the point of view of victimological prevention of crimes, the study of the occurrence of victimization is also of great importance. In legal literature, as well as in scientific research by legal scholars, there are views that victimization is not the possibility of a person being victimized by a crime, but a state in which a person has a high probability of being victimized by a crime, and guilty and innocent types of victimization are distinguished.

References:

1. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Prevention of Crimes". – T., 2014.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 No. PF-6196 "On measures to raise the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of ensuring public security and combating crime to a qualitatively new level".
3. Rustambayev M.X., Niyozova S.S. Victimology General Part. Textbook// Tashkent: University of Public Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2021. – 239 p.
4. Belov G. History of Philosophy of Science. – Moscow: Publishing House of MGU, 2012. – 432 p.
5. Esanova Z.N. "Procedural Features of Judicial Consideration of Disputes Related to Child Education". // Editor-in-chief: Academician, Doctor of Law, Prof. H.R. Rakhmonkulov. – Tashkent.: TYUI Publishing House, 2010. - 289 p.

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

6. Miruktamova F. “Practical proposals for improving national legislation on the juvenile justice system, taking into account international standards” – Tashkent, TYUU, Bulletin of Legal Sciences, 2019, No. 3. – P.147.
7. Varchuk T.V. Victimology: a textbook for university students / T.V. Varchuk, K.V. Vishnevsky; assistant lecturer S.Ya. Lebedeva. – M.: Unita-Dana, 2008. – P. 38
8. Rivman D.V. Criminal victimology. – St. Petersburg, 2002. – P. 26.